

Employability model for students in increasing career opportunities

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 8, 2023
Revised Aug 3, 2024
Accepted Aug 28, 2024

Keywords:

Career
Employability
Peer social support
Resilience
Working college students

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to create and develop an employability model, and the factors that influence be investigated in a proper environment. These students are working at STIE SBI Yogyakarta to determine the adequacy of the model's shape in considering the field-occurring factors. The population of this study was all active students at STIE SBI in Yogyakarta who are currently working. The sample in this study was 101 working STIE SBI students. The technique of sampling in this research used accidental sampling. The data collection instrument used a scale of employability, scale resilience, and the peer social support scale. Data analysis techniques in this study were carried out quantitatively. The analytical method used equation modeling partial least squares path modeling (SEM-PLS) 4.0 through testing the outer and inner models. This study's results were the formation of resilience and peer support models on the employability of working students who appropriate with empirical data. There is a positive and very significant effect of resilience on the employability of working students. The theoretical model formed in this study was an appropriate model that can be used as a valid model reference in developing employability variables.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education has an influence on economic growth with interesting perspectives and innovations that lead to the realization of national development in Indonesia. One of the supports in career planning to acquire better employment potential can be enhancing the quality of education through the collaboration of educators and students. The employment system is created of the institutions and policies acting and simultaneously determining unemployment and employment rates [1]. Joblessness results from an imbalance between the quantity of workers and the amount of job demand.

In Indonesia, one of the contributors to unemployment is college graduates. Not only in Indonesia but abroad, for example, in Brunei Darussalam, the problem of unemployment among university graduates has also become a matter of research [2]. In addition to university graduates who have yet to work, graduates from universities who are already employed but less adaptable and proactive in enhancing their capacity to meet the demands of global competitiveness may cause a drop in the workforce, increasing the unemployment rate. It can also impact the need for better career opportunities. Employability is defined as career-specific proactive, adaptive skills connected to the attitude and conduct of people who are adaptable, proactive, and active [3]. This indicates that employability is important and also needed for workers and job seekers from college graduates.

The quality of graduates as a result of learning to seek individual behavior or efforts in finding a job, the standard of the job chosen, and it is well recognized that employability has an impact on job search outcomes [4]. Employability is a psycho-social construct that embodies individual characteristics that drive cognitively, behaviorally, and affectively to enhance individual interface work [3]. Fugate *et al.* [3] share employability into three separate but interrelated dimensions, namely i) career identity is a picture of a role identity in the form of a job or organization that includes goals, expectations, personality, and values possessed; ii) personal adaptability is the will and ability to change behavior, feelings, and thoughts in response to environmental demands; and iii) social and human capital is an individual's ability to see job opportunities based on factors that exist within themselves.

The role of dimensions of employability is crucial for college graduates as well as higher education institutions themselves because of the ability to realize or actualize employability depending on the individual's internal and external conditions and how those two are related [5]. This situation is an internal and external factor that can affect employability, among others, personality, resilience, calling, future orientation, support from university teaching staff, perspectives of four key stakeholders, social support, skills development, sustainability, career decidedness, independence, and discipline [6]–[17]. Based on the definition above, the influencing factors in this research are resilience and peer social support.

A new framework for supporting competency has been developed in response to the needs and conditions anticipated during the transition from the COVID-19 pandemic to the post-COVID-19 pandemic [18]. The difficulty at this time of change is identifying a person's resilience, defined as their capacity to handle pressure or stress while overcoming anxiety and sadness [19]. According to Connor and Davidson [19] resilience is a character trait that enables an individual to thrive in the face of difficulty.

Research by Connor and Davidson [19] split resilience into five aspects, namely: i) personal competence is a high standard, and tenacity describes the personal competence of individuals where individuals feel as people who can achieve goals even in situations of setbacks or failures; ii) trust in one's instincts is self-confidence is related to calm in acting in the sense that calm individuals tend to be careful in taking a stand on the problems they face; iii) positive acceptance of change and secure relationships represents a positive acceptance of change and having secure relationships with others. The ability to accept difficulties positively and, when in trouble, can relate safely to others; iv) control and factor is the ability to control oneself and achieve self-goals; and v) spiritual influences are spiritually related to the ability always to fight because he believes in God and destiny.

People who have resilience can be shown by the ability to rise from every bad experience and be a failure. This experience will keep people practicing non-stop by evaluating each step to minimize the potential for making mistakes in making decisions [20]. Resilience in college students has an indirect effect on performance through self-efficacy and mindset goals [21]. Furthermore, Fourie and Van Vuuren state that people who have resilience are described as individuals who demonstrate a high degree of flexibility, adaptability, and competence even in difficult career situations [22]. Meanwhile, people with resilience who are low tend to give up easily in the face of intense job competition. When people fail, they often think their chances of success are very low and that they should pursue another career. The most important factor is that their chosen job is unsuitable for their ability; this condition sometimes makes people, as students, unable to develop in their profession [23].

In addition to internal factors, external factors also affect somebody's employability. In this regard, employability in people is influenced by the social support received [24]. Deep encouragement and support are given by peers [10]. Peer social support is the support that contains mutual assistance, sharing, empathy, and friendship, which can foster a sense of belonging and provide positive self-esteem feedback to individuals who assist [25]. Solomon [25] divides peer social support into three aspects, namely: i) emotional support is characterized by the behavior of conveying empathy, caring, attention, positive appreciation, and encouragement to that person; ii) informational support can be characterized by behavior that includes giving suggestions, directions, suggestions, or feedback on how the person is doing; iii) instrumental support is characterized by involving direct assistance such as helping to ease economic or work burdens.

People who receive social support will feel valued and loved by the environment and be assisted when facing a difficulty [26]. People will mostly receive aid in the form of motivation, feedback, and information from the social sphere to ensure they have professional maturity in accomplishing career goals through realizing career planning. In addition, sources of social support have a significant impact on depression and students' quality of life, which is a valuable resource for universities in protecting and supporting students' mental health [27].

Employability plays a significant role for employed students, particularly in enhancing prospects for career advancement. Various problem identifications were carried out to explore the factors that cause workers to find it difficult to meet the current demands of the industry and develop themselves to achieve a better career in the future. There have been many studies discussing employability with the subject of

vocational students, students, and workers, including the research conducted by Donald and Ford [28], McArdle *et al.* [29], Jones *et al.* [30], Mashigo [31], Nabilah *et al.* [11], Adraki *et al.* [32], Hodzic *et al.* [33], Tentama *et al.* [15], Buunaaisie *et al.* [34], and Tentama and Nur [35]. However, these studies used multiple regression analysis with the SPSS program.

Based on the study above, a quantitative approach is needed that does not only analyze the influencing factor of employability but also design and test model employability. The empirical approach to solving problems of employability in the form of designing and testing the model of the influencing factor of employability on student work in terms of resilience and peer social support. Through this strategy, it is established that students aiming to expand suitable job prospects will have access to a model that can be implemented or applied and generalized to a larger group of students (the population).

The novelty of this research was that it was carried out using a model test analysis, which included two processes that distinguished it from previous studies, namely the model design stage and the model testing stage (outer model and inner model). In addition, it involves two psychological variables, namely resilience and peer social support, which are rarely discussed in similar research in the context of model testing (not survey research, correlation, comparison, experiments, and others). In addition, the novelty of this research compared to previous research is to formulate employability specifically for working students. Referring to previous studies, researchers are interested in conducting this research with the aim of designing a model and developing a model of employability and influencing factors; then, it will be tested in a relevant environment for students who work at STIE SBI Yogyakarta. This is to determine the goodness of fit of the designed model with data in the field.

2. METHOD

This study was designed using quantitative research with procedures developed through three stages. The first stage is a preliminary study and preparation of the model, which consists of i) a literature study related to the variables studied either from theoretical studies, previous research results, or field observations related to employability and ii) preparation of research instruments in the form of scale employability, scale resilience, and the scale of peer support based on interviews with students. The second stage was a collection of trial and research data: i) trials of research instruments were carried out on 50 working STIE SBI students and ii) research data collection was carried out on 101 working STIE SBI students. The third stage is testing, which involves testing the inner model with the trial data and the outer model with the final data.

The population of this study is all active students at STIE SBI in Yogyakarta who are currently working. The sample in this study was 101 STIE SBI students who were aged 20 to 40 years. Accidental sampling methods used in research sampling, often referred to as convenience sampling, are sampling methods based on anyone who unintentionally encounters the researcher and may be utilized as a sample if determined to fit the researcher's requirements [36].

Preparation of research instruments in the form of employability scale, resilience scale, and peer support scale. This scale has two directions of statements, namely favorable and unfavorable. There are four categories of statements, namely very inappropriate (STS), not appropriate (TS), appropriate (S), and very appropriate (SS). Favorable items with a score of SS=4, S=3, TS=2, STS=1, otherwise for unfavorable items.

The employability scale was adopted from a scale compiled by Tentama *et al.* [15], which refers to three dimensions of employability proposed by Fugate *et al.* [3]. These dimensions include career identities, personal adaptability, and social and human capital. Examples of items on the scale of employability namely "I feel that my work experience can help me get job opportunities", "I feel that my potential can help achieve success in the future", and "I can adapt to changes in policy". The employability scale consists of nine items with a construct validity test declared valid and reliable with a Cronbach alpha value of 0.887 and a composite reliability value of 0.897.

Scale resilience modified by researchers with a scale developed by Aulia and Baskoro [37], which refers to three aspects of resilience proposed by Connor and Davidson [19], among others: personal competence, trust in one's instincts, positive acceptance of change, and secure relationships, control and factor and spiritual influences. Examples of items on the resilience scale are "Persistent in trying is the way to achieve every target I have", "When experiencing stress, I know the best way to deal with it", and "It's easy for me to be able to adapt to a new environment". The resilience scale consists of 14 items with a construct validity test declared valid and reliable with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.881 and a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.881.composite reliability of 0.887.

The peer social support scale was modified from the scale prepared by Tentama and Riskiyana [38], which refers to three aspects of peer social support proposed by Solomon [25]. These three aspects consist of emotional support, information support, and instrumental support. Examples of items on the peer social support scale are "Friends appreciate the performance I do in campus activities", "When I need assistance, I

can rely on my friends to provide it", and "Friends refuse to cooperate with me". The peer social support scale consists of 16 items with a construct validity test declared valid and reliable with a Cronbach alpha value of 0.936 and a composite reliability value of 0.955.

The methods of data analysis used in this study were quantitative. The analytical method uses structural equation modeling partial least squares path modeling (PLS-SEM) 4.0, which goes through the testing phase of the outer model and testing the inner model. Testing the outer model itself to assess the validity and reliability of the model [39]. The validity test consists of convergent validity and discriminant validity. A convergent validity test assesses the correlation between a construct's indicators. Convergent validity of reflective indicators can be assessed based on the value of the loading factor for each indicator.

The loading factor value used to state whether a construct is valid or not is >0.4 [40], and the average variance extracted (AVE) value is >0.5 [39]. Discriminant validity is seen by comparing the roots of the AVE in each construct with the root values of the AVE in other constructs or variables. Good discriminant validity is indicated by the correlation value of the AVE root of a construct that is greater than the correlation with the AVE root of another construct [39]. There are two methods for doing reliability testing using SEM-PLS analysis: Cronbach alpha and composite reliability. The construct is declared reliable if the Cronbach alpha value is >0.6 [39] and the composite reliability value is >0.7 [40].

This study used the direction of reflective construct indicators, namely indicators that explain the factors that cause the occurrence of something observed. Data analysis in this study used confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) using partial least squared (PLS) through smart PLS software version 3.2.8. developed by Wold in 1974 [41]. The outer model is used to determine the validity and reliability of the construct. Evaluation of the outer model used convergent validity, AVE value, discriminant validity, as well as composite reliability, and Cronbach alpha [39]. The use of the outer model evaluation method is determined by the direction of the indicator. The next stage is evaluating the inner model in three ways, namely; first, by looking at the value of the determinant coefficient (R^2) to measure the level of variation in exogenous to endogenous variables, If $R^2 > 0.2$, then the proposed prediction model is getting better. Second, the value of predictive relevance (Q^2) is used to measure how well the observed values are produced by the model, and also, the estimated parameter Q values $2 > 0$ indicate that the model has predictive relevance. Third, the value of the Goodness of fit index (GoF), which describes the overall model's suitability level, is calculated from the squared residuals of the predicted model compared to the actual data. The criteria for a GoF score of 0.1 is small (GoF small), 0.25 is medium (GoF moderate), and 0.36 is large (GoF large) [39].

The bootstrapping resampling approach devised by Geisser was used to assess the predictive relevance of the exogenous construct hypothesis against endogenous constructs [39]. The test statistic used is the t-test; the t-statistic value at the 5% level is 1.96. Hypothesis testing using smart PLS version 3.00. The hypothesis is accepted if the significance value is p-value < 0.05 , and the hypothesis is rejected if the significance value is > 0.05 .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

The findings of this study are split into two categories: the outcomes of testing the outer model and the outcomes of testing the inner model. Testing the outer model aims to test the measurement model, and testing the inner model aims to test the structural model. The measurement model or outer model shows how the indicators represent the latent variables to be measured, while the structural model or inner model shows the strength of estimates between constructs.

3.1.1. Measurement model test results (outer model)

The measurement model in SmartPLS 3.2.8 is called the outer model. The outer model test aims to specify the relationship between latent variables and their indicators. Outer model analysis includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability, and Cronbach alpha. The results of testing the outer model can be seen in Figure 1.

3.1.2. Convergent validits test

A convergent validity test can be seen from the value of the loading factor on each indicator (item) and the value of AVE. A scale is said to meet convergent validity if the value of the loading factor for each item is >0.4 and the value of the AVE for each variable is >0.5 [40]. Based on the measurement model test results in Figure 1, it is known that the items that meet the loading factor values obtain AVE for each variable. As for the details of the value loading factor and value AVE, each variable can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Output outer model

Figure 2. Loading factor and AVE value

Based on Figure 2, it can be concluded that all variables are declared valid. All research variables have met the requirements for convergent validity because it is known that the loading factor value and AVE value for each variable have met the specified criteria. A more detailed explanation is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Values for the AVE and the loading factor

Variable	Loading factor	AVE	Information
Employability	0.687-0.907	0.530	Valid
Resilience	0.670-0.923	0.517	Valid
Peer support	0.578-0.925	0.534	Valid

3.1.3. Discriminant validity test

Discriminant validity can be observed by comparing the AVE root values between variables. A scale is said to be valid if the AVE root correlation value of each variable is higher than the AVE root correlation value with other variables [40]. Based on the data in Table 2, it is known that the root correlation value of all variables in this study model has satisfied the criteria for discriminant validity, as indicated by the fact that the AVE for each variable is higher than the root correlation value of the AVE with other variables.

Table 2. Comparative value of root AVE on employability, resilience, and peer support

Variable	Employability	Resilience	Peer support
Employability	0.728		
Resilience	0.306	0.719	
Peer support	0.613	0.669	0.731

3.1.4. Reliability

The value of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability can be used to determine the dependability of PLS. If the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha value are both high, then a variable is considered trustworthy, >0.7, and the value 0.6 is still acceptable [40]. In addition, according to Cooper, the AVE value fulfilled >0.5 has supported reliability because, with the fulfillment of construct validity, a valid construct is a reliable construct. Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values in this study can be seen in Table 3. The data in Table 3 showed that the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values for all research variables fulfill the requirements >0.6, so it can be concluded that all constructs or variables in this study fulfill the construct reliability requirements.

Table 3. Cronbach alpha and composite reliability

Variable	Cronbach alpha	Composite reliability	Information
Employability	0.887	0.897	Reliable
Resilience	0.881	0.887	Reliable
Peer support	0.936	0.955	Reliable

3.2. Structural model testing results (inner model)

This study tested the structural model with the inner model after the outer model test was accepted. This is with the aim of ensuring that the structural model that has been built is robust and accurate. The results of testing the inner model can be from the PLS output results in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Output inner model

Based on the output results in Figure 3, it can be said that the results of item selection in each dimension or aspect fulfill the validity and reliability requirements. Further explanation can be seen in the following Table 4. Based on Table 4, the results of the inner model test showed that the factor loadings for each item and AVE value for each variable >0.5 met the criteria of >0.5 , which means that all items are valid. The employability scale consists of 9 valid items. The resilience scale consists of 14 valid items. The peer support scale consists of 16 valid items.

Table 4. Results of the inner model employability output

Variable	Item	Loading factor	AVE	Information
Employability	CI10	0.819	0.530	Valid
	CI16	0.784		Valid
	CI19	0.570		Valid
	PA8	0.734		Valid
	PA14	0.750		Valid
	PA20	0.853		Valid
	SH6	0.687		Valid
	SH12	0.860		Valid
	SH18	0.903		Valid
Resilience	TI2	0.703	0.517	Valid
	TI12	0.828		Valid
	TI7	0.845		Valid
	PC1	0.742		Valid
	PC6	0.775		Valid
	PC11	0.855		Valid
	PR3	0.904		Valid
	PR8	0.923		Valid
	SI5	0.815		Valid
	SI10	0.825		Valid
	SI15	0.830		Valid
	CF4	0.678		Valid
	CF9	0.903		Valid
	CF14	0.670		Valid
Peer support	EM11	0.797	0.534	Valid
	EM16	0.830		Valid
	EM23	0.866		Valid
	EM28	0.723		Valid
	EM34	0.896		Valid
	NS12	0.809		Valid
	NS19	0.889		Valid
	NS24	0.788		Valid
	NS30	0.878		Valid
	NS35	0.758		Valid
	FS3	0.578		Valid
	FS8	0.693		Valid
	FS15	0.892		Valid
	FS20	0.925		Valid
	FS27	0.805		Valid
	FS31	0.920		Valid

3.2.1. Coefficient of determination (R²)

The value of endogenous variables that can be described by exogenous variables or the accuracy of the structural model's predictions is measured by the coefficient of determination [39]. The R-square value is divided into several categories, namely 0.67 (strong), 0.33 (moderate), and 0.19 (weak) [39]. Based on The results of the analysis showed that the R-square value of the model is 0.378.

3.2.2. Predictive relevance (Q²)

Calculating Q² predictive relevance is another method for evaluating the output of structural models. This approach is used in PLS software with blindfolding procedures [39]. The determination shows that a Q² value >0 indicates that the model has good predictive relevance, while Q² <0 indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. The predictive relevance value in this study is 0.286 (moderate).

3.2.3. Goodness of fit index

When validating an overall model, such as by assessing the measurement model and structure model and performing simple measurements for the overall model prediction, the GoF describes the overall level of fit of the model. The GoF value is between 0 and 1, with the interpretation of the value of 0.10 included in

the weak GoF level, 0.25 moderate GoF value, and 0.36 strong GoF value [39]. To measure the goodness of fit, the formula is as follows.

$$GoF = \sqrt{Com.R^2}$$

With: GoF: GoF index, COM: Average communality index, and R²: R-square.

Table 5 shows the R-square value and commonalities.

Table 5. R-square value and commonalities

Variable	R-square
Employability	
Resilience	0.378
Peer support	
Average communality index	0.527

Note: GoF = 0.446 (strong).

Based on the inner model test, it is known that the proposed reflective model (fit) is according to empirical data. The structural model test findings demonstrate that the model of entrepreneurial readiness matches theoretical and actual data in the field (appropriately). This model can be adopted to explain how future orientation and self-efficacy, two exogenous variables, affect endogenous variables like employability. The evaluation results on the inner model can be explained in full in Table 6.

Table 6. Evaluation results of structural model (inner model)

Indicator	Rule of thumb	Result	Information
Coefficient of determination (R ²)	0.67(Strong), 0.33(moderate) and 0.19 (weak)	0.378	The effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables is categorized as moderate
Predictive relevance (Q ²)	Q ² >0=predictive relevance good Q ² <0, predictive relevance poor	0.287	Predictive relevance moderate
Goodness of fit (GoF)	GoF: 0.1 (weak), 0.25 (GoF) moderate, and 0.36 (GoF strong)	0.446	Strong model fit

3.2.4. Hypothesis test

The p-value 0.05 indicates that the hypothesis is accepted when the t-statistic value with alpha 5%, or t-statistics >1.96, is examined, then looking at the original sample value, if the value is (+) then it shows the positive influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables while the value (-) indicated the negative effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables [39]. The following table shows the original sample, t-statistics, and p-value. Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the t-statistic value with an error rate of 5% or a confidence level of 95%, which is obtained by a t-statistic value >1.96. Based on the results of bootstrapping carried out on smart PLS 4.0 can be explained in the Table 7.

Table 7. Hypothesis testing results

Variable	Original sample	T-statistics	p-value	Criteria	Information
Resilience>Employability	0.370	4.112	0.000	0.05 p<0.01	Positive influence and very significant
Peer support>Employability	0.389	4.331	0.000	p<0.01	Positive influence and very significant

Based on the results of the hypothesis test in Table 7, it is known that the results of the first hypothesis test are accepted, based on the R-value=0.378, Q²=0.286, and GoF=0.446, the theoretical model that describes the effect of resilience and peer support on the employability of students who are working is fit with empirical data. Then, the results of the second hypothesis test showed that the hypothesis is accepted, based on the p-value=0.000 and the t-statistic value=4.112 with the original sample value=0.370, indicating a positive and very significant effect of resilience on the employability of students who are working. The results of the third hypothesis test showed that the hypothesis is accepted, based on the p-value=0.000 and the t-statistic value=4.331 with the original sample value=0.389, indicating a positive and very significant influence between peer support on the employability of students who are working.

3.3. Discussion

Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that all hypotheses are accepted. The first hypothesis is accepted with the fulfillment of the coefficient of determination (R²), predictive relevance (Q²), and GoF so that resilience and peer support models are obtained for the employability of students who are working. The model developed demonstrates how peer support and resilience have a substantial impact on employability. This is in line with the GoF obtained, which is at a strong level. The effect of resilience and peer support contributes to employability by 37.8%.

Many previous studies have examined the influence of resilience and peer social support on employability. Research by Upadyaya *et al.* [42] shows that resilience has a significant positive effect on employability. Other studies show that social support also has a significant positive influence on employability [43]. Research results from Forsythe show new data that social capital that regulates their interactions with peers and society can influence self-perceived employability in a higher education student population, balanced by resilience and mindset [44].

The novelty of this research can be observed in the formation of a theoretical model that involves simultaneously (together) the linkages of resilience and peer support to employability. Previous research involved the variables of self-efficacy, job-seeking behavior, and employability in students who attended consulting services [45]. The occupational employability of university graduates in the field of business is influenced by social mobility factors, technical and soft skills, and employability models [46]. A model for verifying student learning methods and examining the relationship between teacher knowledge transfer and student employability from the perspective of social cognitive career theory [47].

The first minor hypothesis test findings indicate that the resilience variable has a significant and favorable impact on employability, which accounts for 37% of the total. Data from related investigations support the findings of this study. Semeijn *et al.* [48] research showed that resilience has a positive effect on employability. Subsequent research conducted by Magrin *et al.* [20] showed that resilience resources have an influence on perceptions of employability. Another study conducted by Ryan *et al.* [49] showed that developing student resilience can impact the development of better employability skills.

Students with high levels of resilience often have the capacity to overcome challenges in the creative industries and are highly motivated to succeed. The findings in this study indicated a contribution to positive acceptance of change and secure relationships, which is excellent in describing variable resilience in students currently working. Students will solve problems successfully and come up with alternate solutions when confronted with severe challenges, complex impediments, or unexpected conditions by adopting a constructive attitude toward job market changes. Working students can develop the ability to face challenges with a positive attitude, a belief in a bigger plan, and a readiness to adapt to new situations. Resilience can be a predictor of high and low employability so the higher the resilience of students, the higher their employability level [11]. The higher a person's resilience, the higher his employability. People who can handle stress and overcome obstacles enthusiastically manage their responsibilities more successfully in a competitive work environment, supporting greater work potential. This helps to open up wider job opportunities and gain greater responsibility that allows one to achieve career goals.

Furthermore, the second minor hypothesis test results showed that the peer social support variable has a positive, very significant effect on employability, with a contribution of 38.9%. Furthermore, the second minor hypothesis test results showed that the peer social support variable has a positive, very significant effect on employability, with a contribution of 38.9%. Social capital that regulates their interactions with peers and society can influence self-perceived employability in a higher education student population [44]. One of the important components of university education that supports employability development is building social relationships that can instill a sense of belonging and a supportive community. These social relationships contribute to employability and graduates value relationships with peers and "fellow student support" [50]. In addition, research conducted by Xia *et al.* [51] showed that social support had a positive effect on employability of college students.

The findings in this study indicated a large contribution of information support in describing the variables of peer support on employability. The relationship of giving and receiving support between peers to achieve employability is higher. Peer social support allows working students to build strong networks and working relationships. In addition, the existence of a peer support program for students can be a model that contributes to the development of graduate career planning and employability [30]. Through peer social support, students can engage in social activities, collaborate, and exchange relevant information. This can help students broaden their professional network and gain better job opportunities. Peers with professional expertise might offer insightful information and suggestions about professions and job prospects. The application of peer learning can promote social mobility and employability in new ways to ensure universities remain relevant in preparing young people to enter the labor market [28]. Therefore, peer social support can help working students understand the job market's needs, industry trends, and effective career development strategies. The size of the trial and research samples is a weakness of the study that readers and

future researchers should be aware of because not all study participants voluntarily filled out the researchers' provided answer sheets. Furthermore, the peer support scale did not specifically include information on support provided by friends within the scope of work or college.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings from this study indicate that: i) the model of the effect of resilience and peer support on employability proposed in this study fits with the empirical data obtained at the research location. ii) There is a positive and very significant effect of resilience on the employability of working students. Higher resilience indicates increased employability. iii) There is a positive and very significant influence between peer support and the employability of working students. Employability increased with the level of peer support. Thus, the model in this study can be used to develop and strengthen employability, both theoretically and practically, especially for working students.

Suggestions for scientific development are: i) For future researchers, pay attention to other factors of social support, such as lecturers, family, and co-workers. ii) For STIE SBI to improve students' employability in the teaching and learning process, pay attention to the two independent factors investigated in this study. The development of skills from instruction, direction, or assistance from others can be done as a follow-up.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express gratitude to the Directorate General for Higher Education, Research and Technology, Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, for providing research funding in 2023. Implementation and funding of research through contracts numbered 181/E5/PG.02.00.PL/2023 dated June 19, 2023, 0423.11/LL5-INT/AL.04/2023 dated June 22, 2023, and 046/PPS-PTM/LPPM UAD/VI/2023 dated June 24, 2023. Thus, this research can be carried out smoothly and completed on time.

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